

STUDYING BIOLOGICALLY ACTIVE SUPPLEMENTS AND THEIR DOSAGE FORMS

Narzullaeva Mehrangiz Azizkhonovna
Samarkand state medical University
Assistant of the Department of
Organization pharmaceutical business

Annotation

In this article you will learn what dietary supplements are. The benefits of dietary supplements in nutrition, composition and content of natural substances. Biologically active additives (BAA) to food are biologically active substances and their compositions intended for direct intake with food or inclusion in food products. Legally, dietary supplements belong to food and are not medicines. Dietary supplements are a form of registration, like medicines. The same substances can be registered both as dietary supplements and as medicines. Dietary supplements are used as an additional source of biologically active substances (dietary fiber, vitamins, minerals, amino acids) to eliminate their deficiency and optimize the diet.

Key words: Minerals, Vitamins, Probiotics, Essential Fatty Acids

There are no standards for the production of dietary supplements. Their quality control consists only of assessing their safety as food products. Dietary supplements do not undergo clinical trials. In Russia there is no integral system and regulatory framework for regulation in the field of dietary supplements turnover. As a result, dietary supplements have become the object of uncontrolled commercial activity with unfair and aggressive advertising. Today, many dietary supplements are advertised as medicines, but in fact they are not. Commercial companies often produce dietary supplements in an artisanal way. The

interpretation of the term “dietary supplement” has become ambiguous both among consumers and among medical personnel, this often leads to serious misconceptions.

Classification of dietary supplements

There are different classifications of dietary supplements depending on their composition and physiological action, as well as the methods of obtaining and the form of production of dietary supplements, therefore any classification of dietary supplements is quite arbitrary

- Minerals
- Vitamins
- Probiotics
- Sports nutrition
- Essential fatty acids
- Amino acids
- Natural dietary supplements

Minerals are chemical elements necessary to ensure the normal functioning of a living organism.

Vitamins are organic compounds necessary in very limited quantities for the normal functioning of a living organism. Vitamins cannot be synthesized by the body itself (with rare exceptions) and must be obtained from food. In their absence or deficiency, the normal development of the human or animal body is disrupted. In this case, vital processes are either suspended or do not occur at all.

About 500 different types of microorganisms live in the human intestine, totaling about 50 trillion. Probiotics, when considered as dietary supplements, are used for therapeutic purposes to normalize intestinal microflora and immunomodulation. The most well-known types of probiotics are bifidobacteria and lactobacilli.

Sports nutrition is a nutritional supplement created to provide the athlete's

body with essential vitamins, minerals and nutrients. Sports nutrition is fundamentally different from regular nutrition and does not replace it. The composition of sports nutrition may vary depending on the goals set in a particular sport (bodybuilding, weightlifting, athletics, martial arts, fitness, etc.). It can be aimed at improving athletic performance, achieving optimal body weight, increasing muscle mass, reducing body fat percentage, etc.

The most common sports nutrition: protein blends, carbohydrate-protein blends, branched chain amino acids (BCAAs), phosphatidylserine, glutamine, arginine, essential fatty acids, creatine and weight loss products. These and many other products are sold as sports supplements.

Fats are complex compounds of glycerol and fatty acids. Fatty acid molecules are chains of carbon atoms linked together. If all the carbon bonds in a fatty acid are single (C-C), the fatty acid is called saturated; fatty acids with one double bond (C=C) are called monounsaturated; with two or more double bonds (C=C=C) are called polyunsaturated.

There are two classes of essential polyunsaturated fatty acids: omega-3 unsaturated fatty acids and omega-6 unsaturated fatty acids. Both groups are considered essential for the human body, since they are not synthesized in it and must be supplied with food. The most essential fatty acids are alpha-linolenic acid (ALA), which is an omega-3, and linoleic acid (LA), which is an omega-6. From alpha-linolenic acid, the body can synthesize two other important omega-3 polyunsaturated acids: eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA) and docosahexaenoic acid (DHA). ALA is found in large quantities in flaxseed oil. Dietary sources of DHA and EPA include fatty marine fish, while dietary supplement capsules contain fish oil or krill oil.

Proteins are complex organic substances whose molecules consist of amino acids connected in a chain by peptide bonds. In most cases, living organisms use 20 standard amino acids to synthesize proteins. Eight of these amino acids are

considered essential because they cannot be synthesized by the human body and must be obtained through food[. The following amino acids are considered essential: valine, isoleucine, leucine, lysine, methionine, threonine, tryptophan and phenylalanine.

The ninth amino acid, histidine, was previously considered essential only for children, but according to modern concepts it is also considered essential for adults. Nonessential amino acids are produced in the body from other amino acids, but the need for them may arise depending on the age and lifestyle or condition of the person. Essential amino acids are: asparagine, alanine, arginine, glycine, aspartic acid, glutamic acid, glutamine, serine, proline, tyrosine, cysteine. Amino acids are sold as dietary supplements, both individually and in various complexes.

In addition to the 20 standard amino acids, there are many other amino acids and substances that are similar in structure to amino acids and are often considered together with them

Literature

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